

Development of Triathlon Sports Tourism Selera Sport

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Abstract

This research aimed to analyze the development of Triathlon sports tourism in attracting people to travel and exercise on Kurenai Beach. This research method used an experimental design. This research was to develop a product or model to develop Triathlon sports tourism. The subjects were the people who visited Kurenai Beach. Data collection techniques used questionnaires, interviews, and documentation. The data analysis technique used the Paired sample t-test and the N-Gain test. The results showed that the triathlon sport development model in this study was called Triathlon sports tourism Selera sport. The results of the hypothesis test showed that statistically the sig value obtained from the paired test was 0.000. This value was less than 0.05 so that means the hypothesis was accepted. There was a significant difference in the average score before and after treatment, so it meant that the Triathlon sports tourism Selera sport model could increase people's interest in traveling. The tourism development model to increase the interest in traveling for the people of Kurenai Beach was the Triathlon sports tourism Selera sport model. This development model was effective in increasing tourism interest so that it could increase the income of tourism managers and local governments.

Keywords: *Triathlon Sports Tourism Selera Sport.*

INTRODUCTION

Sports tourism is the utilization of two disciplines namely tourism and sports. Both are brought together and developed in the tourism and sports industries to have an impact on economic growth (Isnaini & Hasbi, 2021). Sports tourism can be interpreted as sports activities carried out when traveling or living in places outside their usual environment (Gonzales-Garcia et al., 2018). The main characteristics of this activity are holidays, free time, and involvement in sports activities actively and passively. Exercise is an important activity during visits to the destination (Millet et al., 2011). Sports are the activity of choice for tourists while on vacation because sports attract tourists with the values contained and the benefits of fitness in them (Lepers, 2019). Tourism is a sum of phenomena and relationships arising from the interaction of tourists, business buyers, host governments, and host communities in the process of attracting and accommodating these tourists and visitors (Isnaini & Hasbi, 2021). Tourism as 'a process related to the redistribution of economic resources, from home communities to host communities which involves travel to recreational destinations. Tourism is expected to increase with future tourist arrivals growing to 1.6 billion in 2020 with an average growth rate of 4.3% (Sihana, 2022). Sports tourism provides a model of 1), sports opportunities, 2), holiday activities. 3), sports training. 4), event goers, and 5), sports holidays. Activity holidays, although perhaps not originally intended to take place, have come to imply outdoor adventures or country activities such as rock climbing, potholing, or hiking or trekking.

Sport can be a major tourism decision factor, even if it is not the main purpose of the trip. In such cases, sports can become a determining factor between several different tourist destinations, in essence, it is a 'Unique Selling Proposition' for the provider (Praisra et al., 2021). Sports tourism is a sport in which sport itself may be a method of transportation for travel, such as hiking, cycling and sailing. Taking the latter case as an example, sailing sports tourism can be divided into two distinct categories: where the boat itself is the transportation and accommodation for the journey; and where the cruise takes place at the same place (for example, on a lake or coastal site) and accommodation is provided nearby.

Motivations are related to sport participation and tourism and there is ample evidence in this review that the motivations of both sports participants and tourists share a number of common traits which might offer some insight into the uniqueness of sport tourism. "Socio-psychological dominates the sport motivation literature and it is this perspective that most closely reflects the body of literature trying to explain the reasons for individual involvement in tourism activities. People's motives for exercising are many and varied. Such activities can be generalized as well as unique to individuals, and dynamic in that they change over time. Such motivation includes psychological, social and philosophical perspectives. A large amount of research on the motives behind sports participation involves individual characteristics-interests, needs, goals and personality. exercise includes goals such as weight control, physical appearance and generally maintaining the body in good physical condition to maximize life experiences.

Such health benefits are also definitely related to the notion of enjoyment, pleasure satisfaction, and joy of positive affective experiences that some people have (Sudiana, 2019). In addition to the associated physical and psychological benefits they provide, some authors also offer philosophical reasons for explaining people's desire for pleasure in terms of the desire for the 'good life. Sport, for example, can be considered as an important component of certain lifestyles and, furthermore, can reflect developments in contemporary society and be used by individuals as a means of escaping from the pressures of everyday life. These two motives are equally important elements in the tourism motivation literature. Vacations are now considered an important component of the modern lifestyle, with people preparing to give up other items instead of the annual vacation.

Sports training, high-market sports holidays, activity holidays, sports opportunities on public holidays, and sports viewing (Praisra et al., 2021). Although these categories are proposed as demand types, they are essentially supply-side categorizations of sports holidays. Sports tourism can be active or passive (i.e. includes involvement in the activity itself or as a spectator), and that sport may be the primary purpose of the trip or be 'incidental' to holidays that have other primary objectives. 'Sports-relevant tourism' is divided into leisure and non-leisure travel, which are divided into active and passive travel respectively before the subdivision. A useful concept introduced in this categorization is the distinction made under passive exercise between casual and expert observers. Sport is a tourist destination with one of the most authentic types of attractions. The link between culture and sport takes many forms, from the juxtaposition of cultural performances with sporting events to the central role played by sport as an embodiment of contemporary culture. The concept of place, as suggested by geographers, raises important questions about the field of sport and tourism. This relates to the use of sport to promote tourism destinations in various markets, and the significant challenges associated with the commodification and corporatization of culture.

The environment relates to the natural and built resources used to support activities, as well as the impact of various activities on these resources. The community explores the geography of natural and built resources related to sports and tourism (Supriyanto, 2022). Many outdoor sports tend to depend on specific landscapes and/or climatic conditions while other types of sports are more mobile and feature standard, site-buildable facilities designed to maximize market access. The distance decay function of sports tourism can also be mediated by such things as the quality of opponents and the importance of competition or, in the case of non-competitive sports, the accessibility, availability, and costs of engaging in the selected sporting activity at a destination. Factors that can interfere with the distance decay function of sport tourism are not well understood and need academic attention.

Sports tourism takes place in an environment of complex spatial parameters. Different sports depend to different degrees on the availability and quality of natural and/or built resources. While some sports are rigidly associated with specific, immovable natural resources, others are relatively free of resource constraints and may be located where proximity to population concentrations offers the greatest competitive advantage. The distance-time-cost threshold also shapes the spatial travel patterns of sports tourists. However, the reach of the sports tourism market and travel flows are affected by various factors that are not well understood. This ensures that various questions arise from discussing the spatial elements of sport and tourism.

An important characteristic of sport is that it involves some active pursuit and such activity requires special resources. Such resources may involve certain environments or certain facilities but what is important is that they are not everywhere; they are found in certain locations. Of course, some sources are more widespread than others. While many routines allow people to run or cycle, facilities for activities such as skiing or rock climbing are less widespread. However, while resources are more readily available, their quality can vary with high quality resources only being found in a few locations. Football, played and watched in local parks, is a very different experience to one encountered in Premier League stadiums; and, as indicated at the start of the text, cycling through the attractive landscape of national parks stands in stark contrast to cycling along busy city and city streets.

Sports participation often requires travel, some of which may be obviously traveling to destinations far from the home environment, and the purpose of this section is to examine the special characteristics of certain places by focusing on two specific perspectives. The first concerns the physical characteristics and spatial patterns of sports venues, and the second concerns the way such venues are viewed and valued culturally.

The development of village potential based on sports tourism aims to encourage villages to creatively manage and empower the people in the village so that the community gets additional (economic) income (Sihana, 2022). One of the developments that can be carried out in tourist attractions is to build several tourism businesses (Supriyanto, 2022). The tourism business includes the development of a tourism business including tourist attractions, tourism areas, tourist transportation services, tour travel services (Fajar & Dwi, 2022). Managers can also open a food and beverage provider business, provide accommodation, organize entertainment and recreational activities, organize meetings, incentive trips, conferences, exhibitions, tourism information services, tourism consulting services, tour guide services, water tourism and spa (Nasution et al., 2022)

One of the sports that is categorized as sports tourism is Triathlon or also known as Trilomba (Wicker et al., 2013). Triathlon is a systematically planned physical activity that aims to develop and improve the individual organically, neuromuscularly, perceptually, cognitively and emotionally and develops into a competition consisting of a series of sports, namely swimming, bicycle racing, and running (Mason et al., 2019).

Botubarani village is one of the areas in the Tomini Bay area in Gorontalo Province, especially Bone Bolango District, and Kabila Bone District. The natural resources located on the coast of Botubarani Village can be developed sustainably if the surrounding community can maintain their sustainability. In addition, Botubarani Village is an area that has this strategic position, located in the waters of Tomini Bay and traversed by the Southern Cross National Route which connects Gorontalo Province and North Sulawesi Province and is directly adjacent to the Bogani Nani Wartabone National Park. This is very important because the development of sports tourism requires superior and reliable human resources in designing various kinds of sports activities so that they become tourist attractions that are worth selling because they have economic values (Hemmonsbey & Tichaawa, 2020).

The results of Rahmadio's research (2022) Tourism development has a positive and significant influence on development. The development and management of a sports tourism destination require cooperation between parties from the government or from the private sector. The results of the same research Praisra et al., (2021) the development of sports tourism in water areas increase the attractiveness of the public to visit tourist attractions. Visitors can follow the sports offered and get entertainment at the same time. The development of Triathlon sports tourism Selera sportaims to increase the interest of the public to travel on the Kurenai monitor.

METHOD

This research method uses a one-group pretest-posttest experimental design. Triathlon sports tourism Selera sportdevelopment model uses the 10-step development model proposed by (Sugiyono, 2019). The research location was carried out at Kurenai Beach, Gorontalo Province. The variable in this study is the public's interest in visiting Kurenai. The pretest-posttest design was used to analyze the differences given by the sports tourism development model to the interest in traveling before and after being given treatment. The subjects in this study were 60 visitors to Kurenai Beach tourism. The data collection technique used is using questionnaires and documentation. Data analysis technique using paired sample t-test.

RESULTS

Sports and tourism are two disciplines that can be combined so that they have multiple strengths and effects on economic growth in Indonesia in general. Therefore sports tourism is currently receiving great attention from both the government, the private sector, the sports industry, the tourism industry, academia and the wider community. Sport Tourism or Tourism for sports is a new paradigm in the development of tourism and sports in Indonesia. Sports tourism is able to show its potential as something interesting, so that it can create a tourist attraction that can make multicultural tourism.

A tourist attraction is everything that is found in a tourist destination which is an attraction so that people have a greater interest in visiting a tourist destination. In order for a tourist destination to have attractiveness, the area must also have several conditions that must

be possessed, namely: (1) There is something that can be seen, (2) There is an activity to be carried out, (3) There is something that can be seen. buy. This is very important because the development of sports tourism requires superior and reliable human resources in designing various kinds of sports activities so that they become tourist attractions that are worth selling because they have economic values. The development of sports tourism in Indonesia is currently a demand, so it must consider the supply that must be available when demand increases.

One of the sports that are categorized as sports tourism is Triathlon or what is also called a triathlon is a systematically designed physical activity that aims to develop and improve individuals organically, neuromuscularly, perceptually, cognitively, and emotionally and develop into a competition consisting of sports competitions, namely swimming, cycling, and running. This competition is carried out irrationally in one unit of time. This trilomba is also a speed-time competition where participants must be able to share their energy in each stage.

This triathlon was first created by Scott Tinley and was first held in France around the 1920s. At first, the Trilomba was held as part of training for running athletes. The first triathlon was held at Mission Port San Diego in 1974. The flow of the triathlon was sequential, with a transition from swimming to cycling and cycling to running. The winner of this competition is calculated based on the fastest race finisher including the transition time. The Triathlon Model sport was developed because one of them is to balance the physique of the athletes (Spiker et al., 2012). Sports athletes who always run continuously, the burden on the feet will be bigger and heavier. This can be reduced by doing bicycle exercise. The legs are used with a different function, namely not for running, so in addition to reducing the burden on the feet it can also be useful for relieving stress due to continuous running.

This competition has varying distances in the Olympics. First, there is the Sprint Distance where the distance is 750m for swimming, 20km for cycling, and 5km for running. Then there is the Standard or Olympic Distance with a distance of 1500m for swimming, 40km for cycling, and 10km for running. This triathlon competition is generally held near open waters such as seas, lakes, rivers, and outdoor artificial ponds. The bicycle routes can take locations on the highway or off-road for cross-triathlons. The running route itself can be done on the highway, pedestrian, beach, land, and in the mountains

In Indonesia, this triathlon has often been held, including in Jakarta, Bogor, Surabaya, Bali, Bintan, Palembang, Pariaman, Sungailiat, Belitung, Jepara, Sibolga, Central Tapanuli, and Pangandaran. Therefore it is necessary to do a needs analysis. This needs analysis was carried out by observing the sports activities of one of the triathlon disciplines, namely running sports for the general public in urban areas and the trading needs of small and medium-sized businesses that occur in the field, then conducting a literature study.

The results of observations of running sports by the general public, namely in urban areas of the city of Gorontalo, and small and medium scale traders in the tourist destination of Tomini Bay, Gorontalo Province, which is on the Kurenai tourist beach, Botubarani Village, Kabila Bone District, Bone Bolango Regency. From the results of observations, it can be concluded that the lack of socialization and multilateral sports tourism activities that are sufficient, low stimulants of sports tourism activities, activity implementing operators and learning and socialization technical facilitators who utilize resources, utilization and utilization of the natural wealth of the Gorontalo regional government to be used as tourism products that will contribute to Regional Original Revenue.

The results of the observations above, the researcher will develop sports tourism for the implementation of triathlon activities. Researchers hope that the products produced will be able to: (1) improve the quality of triathlon or triathlon sports tourism, so that it is hoped that it can increase public interest in enjoying the benefits of physical fitness so that people can improve their muscle and bone health, increase energy, to improve mood, (2) Develop a model of learning facilities so that it can attract the interest of some community groups as operators implementing sports activities so that they can deepen the knowledge of Triathlon and use it for the benefit of developing sports tourism businesses, (3) and assist local governments as facilitators in preparing Triathlon learning facilities by using this means.

The data used to support the development of the Triathlon sports tourism Selera sport model used 2 initial data collection methods, namely conducting group discussion forums and conducting preliminary studies in the field. The results of the data collection analysis of the two techniques can be described as follows.

Forum Group Discussion

In the early stages, a group discussion forum was held with sports academics, sports administrators of the Gorontalo Regional Government, tourism administrators of the Gorontalo Regional Government, and community leaders around the Wasata area on Kurenai Beach. The group discussion forum discusses the current development of the game Sepaktakraw and the problems that exist. Based on the group discussion forum, information was obtained that sports tourism in the Gorontalo area does not yet exist in tourist locations. The results of the group discussion forum obtained information that the management of tourist attractions, especially monitoring Kurenai, was less attractive for public entertainment. This makes the number of visitors to this tourist spot not as expected. The people who visit every day are only young people who are dating and the number is not maximized.

The results of the focus group discussion obtained information that existing tourism required a management and development strategy that could attract the public's interest. According to representatives of sports management, information was also obtained that people's interest in exercising was getting lower. Digital and internet developments are one of the factors that make the current generation of people not like to exercise. This must be made a solution so that people's interest in exercising increases and they are interested in exercising regularly in particular.

Based on the results of the initial focus group discussion, the researchers conducted a focus group discussion with experts from academics and government representatives to develop a model that could provide solutions to these main problems. The need assessment form was prepared based on the needs of the results of the initial focus group discussion, namely the need for a model for developing tourist attractions along with sports. It is intended that the developed model can provide solutions to 2 problems, namely the problem of interest in traveling and interest in sports.

The results of the focus group discussion attended by 20 participants can be described as follows.

Table 1: Results of Focus Group Discussion

No	Aspects	Answer “ Yes “ “ (person)	Answer “ No “ (person)
1	Sports Tourism Development	18	2
2	Tourism that can attract the wider community	20	0
3	Sports that can attract the wider community	18	0
4	Developing Triathlon for sports tourism	16	4
5	Sports tourism location on Kurenai Beach	15	5

Source: Results of focus group discussion

Based on the results of the focus group discussion, it is known that 90% of all participants in the focus group discussion provided input to develop sports tourism. This answer is the majority answer or the most answers compared to the others. Other participants gave answers to developing cultural tourism. The researcher in this case took the answer that was most chosen and suggested by the participants, namely sports tourism. This choice is in accordance with the problems faced by the Gorontalo regional government, namely problems in the field of tourism and sports interest.

In the aspect of having to develop tourism that can attract the wider community, 100% of answers agree with this. However, to develop a sport that can attract the wider community, a 90% answer is obtained. This was due to another desire by the participants, namely to develop the existing culture so that it would be known by the wider community. From these two aspects, the researchers decided to develop tourism and sports that could attract the wider community by combining these aspects of tourism and sports.

Aspects of the types of sports developed based on focus group discussions provide answers to developing triathlons. According to the participants, this is in accordance with the physical and natural conditions that exist in the Gorontalo Regency government area. Natural resources that have not been managed properly are feasible and good to develop into triathlon sports tourism. One of the reasons that made the choice of this type of sport was that this type of sports tourism did not yet exist in Gorontalo so that when it was developed it could attract the interest of the wider community. This can develop tourism in particular and the sports sector in general.

Field Study

After conducting focus group discussions with experts, researchers then made observations in the field to answer and implement the ideas that had been obtained from focus group discussions. The results of observations in the field note that the Kurenai beach tourist spot is indeed empty of visitors. The beach is not managed properly and tends not to be well cared for by both the manager and the government. Observation results also obtained information that the current condition of the beach is less attractive to the public because there is no sale value being offered. Visitors only come to see the waves outside making it one of the less attractive factors.

Based on the results of interviews with beach tourism managers, information was obtained that up to the time of these observations, there had been no interesting policies or management changes. The government has not issued a policy for optimal management of the beach. According to the beach manager, it can actually be used for swimming competitions, for example. The sea water is clear and the depth is not too deep and the waves are not big, very suitable for the visitor's swimming area. However, no one has yet developed the idea.

The results of interviews with community leaders around Kurenai Beach obtained information that actually existing natural resources have a sale value for tourists. The scenery that the beach area offers is beautiful if it is well developed and attracts the community. However, in reality these natural resources have not been properly utilized by the government. In addition, many local people who are unemployed do not have a job. Most people use marine products such as fish to be sold in the market.

The government needs to develop a model of tourist attractions that can attract visitors, and make good use of natural resources, as well as its human resources. Natural resources that are developed properly and correctly will bring in visitors in tourist areas so that indirectly human resources benefit. Based on the results of the field study, it can be concluded as follows.

1. The tourism sector needs to be developed to attract people to visit it
2. Development of tourism in accordance with the physical and social conditions of existing natural resources
3. Development of tourism based on uniting sports in order to increase interest in sports as well as for the community.
4. Development of tourism and sports in accordance with physical conditions
5. Development of tourism that can utilize human resources in the area around tourist attractions.

Based on the results of these observations and analysis, the researchers decided to develop sports tourism that could attract people's interest and be by existing natural conditions. The sport tourism developed is the Selera sport triathlon.

Based on the results of the development of the Selera sport triathlon sports tourism design, it can be designed as shown below.

Figure 1: Design of Triathlon Sport Tourism Development Model, Selera Sport

The model that has been tested on research subjects is then tested for the effectiveness of the model. Paired sample t-test was used to analyze the effectiveness of the developed model. Based on the results of the paired sample t test, the following results are obtained.

Table 1: Hypothesis Test Results

		Mean	Deviation	T count	Sig
Pair 1	posttest	59.33	29.12	124.319	.000
	pretest	30.22			

Based on the results of the hypothesis test, it is known that the average before and after the large-scale trial of the Selera sport triathlon sports tourism model has increased by 29.12. The average at the pretest stage was only 30.22, increasing to 59.33 at the posttest stage. From these results, a t count of 124,319 was also obtained with a sig value of 0,000. if you see the sig value is less than 0.05, it means that the hypothesis is accepted. There is a significant difference in the average before and after large-scale product trials. That is, the development of the triathlon sports tourism model, Sport Taste, is effective in achieving the goals stated in the model. The development of a sports tourism model is that it can increase the public's interest in drawing and exercising, boosting the economy, and increasing local revenue through sports tourism.

DISCUSSION

Tourism is a sector that is superior to the Indonesian nation because it has many natural resources that can be developed into attractive tourist spots for visitors. Indonesia is a maritime country that has many beaches so natural resources have high potential for tourist attractions (Hidayat, 2022). If this tourism is developed to attract people to visit, it will indirectly have a big positive impact on the community and the government (Moradi et al., 2022).

Botubarani village is one of the areas in the Tomini Bay area in Gorontalo Province, especially Bone Bolango District, and Kabila Bone District. The natural resources located on the coast of Botubarani Village can be developed sustainably if the surrounding community can maintain their sustainability. In addition, Botubarani Village is an area that has this strategic position, located in the waters of Tomini Bay and traversed by the Southern Cross National Route which connects Gorontalo Province and North Sulawesi Province and is directly adjacent to the Bogani Nani Wartabone National Park. This is very important because the development of sports tourism requires superior and reliable human resources in designing various kinds of sports activities so that they become tourist attractions that are worth selling because they have economic values.

Based on the results of the development of the triathlon sports tourism model, Selera Sport shows that the model is effective in increasing the attractiveness of people to visit tourist attractions. Prior to being given a triathlon sports tourism development model, the community's taste for sports was less interested in coming to Kurenai beach resorts.

However, after being given a model for the development of triathlon sports tourism, sports tastes on Kurenai Beach made people interested in traveling. This model was developed so that people not only enjoy traveling but also make it interesting for people to exercise.

The concept of sports tourism cannot be separated between sports and tourism. But the two are a blend that complements each other when developed in an area. This is because Sport can be a major tourism decision factor, even if it is not the main purpose of the trip. In such

cases, sport can be a determining factor between a number of different destinations, in essence, it is a '*Unique Selling Proposition*' for the provider

Sports can also become part of tourism planning after the choice of destination has been made. In such cases, there may be an element of sports participation or a visit to an event, facility or attraction that is considered a 'must see' or 'must do' activity when visiting a particular area. Sports Participation Tourism where sport is the main purpose of the trip is probably the most obvious of which basically refers to sports holidays, which is what most people think of when they encounter the term sports tourism (Usmanova, 2022). As in the previous category, there is some overlap with other types of sports tourism, particularly luxury sports tourism. Overlap with other categories is best handled with exceptions. In this regard, active participation in sporting events, except at the most basic level, is excluded from this category, as are extended forms of teaching or training. Therefore, this category includes the rest of multi-sport or single-sport participation tourism.

One of the sports that are categorized as sports tourism is the Triathlon or what is also called the Trilomba is a systematically designed physical activity that aims to develop and improve individuals organically, neuromuscularly, perceptually, cognitively, and emotionally and develop into a competition consisting of series of sports, namely swimming, cycling and running.

The results of content research are in line with research conducted by Rahmadio (2022) which shows that the development of tourist attractions can increase the attractiveness of visitors. Developed tourist attractions have a positive impact, especially on the economy around tourist attractions. The economy has increased evenly in the surrounding areas due to the large number of visitors visiting tourist attractions. Finally, the velocity of money at tourist attractions becomes high and has a positive impact on the local community. The results of research conducted by Toineno and Wani (2018) show that the development of tourism in a football stadium environment has proven to increase tourists visiting these tourist attractions. Visitors come not only to see football matches but also to tour the area around the stadium. The research results of Praisra et al., (2021) show that the development of sports tourism in river areas increases the attractiveness of people to visit river tourist attractions. Visitors can follow the sports offered and get entertainment at the same time.

The results of research conducted by Sudiana (2019) show that sports tourism has a positive impact on society. Sports tourism attracts people to travel because they can get healthy as well as get sports. Research by Gonzales et al., (2018) shows that sports tourism can increase people's interest in traveling. The positive impact is obtained by the community around the tourist attractions and the government that manages the tourist attractions.

The sports tourism development model for the triathlon Selera Sport which was developed at Kurenai Beach was developed based on existing natural resources. These results are supported by research conducted by Pauweni et al., (2022) that Gorontalo has good potential to develop sports tourism. Gorontalo has the potential for active sports tourism and passive sports tourism.

CONCLUSION

Travel and sports are two elements that can be combined to complement each other. Tourism and sports both have an important role in society. The results of the analysis show that the development of sports tourism can be carried out to develop tourism on Kurenai Beach. Based on the results of research and development of sports tourism models, it can be concluded as follows.

1. The development model for triathlete sports tourism on Kurenai Beach is developed based on existing natural and socio-cultural resources. The sports tourism development model is a modification of the triathlon sport related to the distance traveled and complementary facilities. Triathlon sports tourism is developed not only for the benefit of athletes but also for the benefit of the general public. The triathlon sports tourism development model is named Selera sport sports tourism.
2. The triathlon sports tourism model Selera sport is effective in increasing public interest in visiting Kurenai Beach. Models can attract the traveling public because sports are presented in a new way, namely while traveling. People who are interested in traveling a lot will indirectly increase the number of tourist visitors. This phenomenon will improve the economy through the management of tourist attractions and increase local revenue earned by the local government.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. The results of the research can provide an overview to the government of the model for the development of sports tourism in the Gorontalo government area.
2. The results of the study provide an overview that Kurenai Beach tourism in Gorontalo has the potential to be developed into a triathlon sports tour to increase the local government's original income and can open jobs for the local community. The community will get increased economic income when there is tourism with many visitors because they are enthusiastic about triathlon sports tourism.

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